

Agronomic evaluation of dry-seeded rice varieties under rainfed-bunded conditions

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The direct or dry-seeding technique of establishing a rice crop increases the production potential of rainfed-bunded rice-based cropping systems. The technology has had a great impact in areas where the rainfall duration is limited and the supply is sufficient to establish only one regular transplanted rice crop for about 2 months after initial wet season rains. A dry-seeded rice crop established during initial rains can still be followed by either an early maturing rice crop or upland crops such as legumes and other cereals. This study was conducted to identify improved rice varieties that are suitable for dry seeding.

Twenty-six IRRI rice cultivars were direct seeded in thoroughly prepared, dry, bunded fields after initial light rains at IRRI on 25 May 1977. Rice seeds at 100 kg/ha were drilled in small furrows made with a lithao (wooden-type furrow opener), spaced at 25 × 25 cm, and covered with soil from the ridges. Soil fertility was maintained by a basal furrow application before seeding of 45-45-45 kg/ha of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O and a side-dressing of 55-0-0 kg/ha at 55 days after seeding (DS). Weeds were adequately controlled by a butachlor spray immediately after planting and two later hand weedings. Azodrin 168 and Gamma Hytox were periodically sprayed and carbofuran granules were broadcast at 65 DS to preclude or minimize insect damage. Hinosan was sprayed at 65 DS to control fungus diseases. There was no supplemental irrigation. Rainwater

Yield and agronomic characteristics of 26 dry-seeded rices under rainfed-bunded conditions. IRRI, 1977 wet season.

Designation	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Days ^b to		Plant ht (cm)	Lodging ^c rating	Tillers (no./sq m)
		Heading	Maturity			
IR36	5.01	83	111	90	2	610
IR28	4.38	74	99	100	1	481
IR2823-399-5-6	4.22	95	132	106	3	490
IR4432-52-6-4	3.88	93	121	106	4	462
IR2058-78-1-3-2-3	3.84	90	121	113	4	514
IR4427-119-6-1	3.77	88	115	102	4	483
IR42	3.69	110	134	116	3	531
IR38	3.60	92	120	100	4	582
IR4722-36-1	3.60	93	117	108	4	541
IR1561-228-33	3.54	82	115	93	1	611
IR4432-38-6	3.41	93	120	107	6	440
IR4442-143-2-1	3.27	90	118	116	8	411
IR3941-25-1	3.22	78	106	101	1	655
IR4707-123-3	3.21	85	118	95	4	594
IR4440-165-2-4	3.04	87	124	96	2	517
IR4442-45-2-1	2.98	85	117	98	2	503
IR4227-107-1-3	2.89	94	123	119	6	376
IR2307-217-2-3	2.81	77	103	91	1	593
IR40	2.74	92	118	109	9	569
IR4422-164-3-6	2.74	94	122	116	2	493
IR5201-122-2	2.48	99	130	106	4	386
IR4227-18-3-2	1.93	108	140	138	5	333
IR4613-54-5	1.69	108	139	136	6	2 a4
IR4816-70-1	1.47	100	131	127	8	263
IR4608-6-2	0.87	104	132	141	7	285
Mean	3.15	92	122	109	4	478
LSD (.05)	1.26	3	5	7	4	94
CV (%)	24.4	2.0	2.8	3.9	54.9	12

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b From seeding. ^c 1 = no lodging; 9 = completely lodging.

accumulated in the fields for only a few days after heavy rains during the late vegetative stage and after the heading stage. Thus, prevailing conditions were semi lowland.

IR36 yielded highest (5 t/ha), followed by IR28 and IR2823-399-5-6 (both more than 4 t/ha) (see table). The outstanding cultivars generally tended to be early maturing and to have other good agronomic characteristics: they are relatively short (90–116 cm), nonlodging to slightly lodging, with high tillering

ability (at least 400 tillers/sq m), high panicle production (about 400 panicles/sq m), prolific grain production (83 to 130 grains/panicle, at least 70% filled), and dry-grain weight of about 18 to 26 g/1,000 seeds. Lodging appeared to be the factor most difficult to control; lodging due to strong typhoons that occurred during the vegetative stage limited the yields of most rices. Yields would probably have been higher if the relatively late-maturing rices had not lodged. **W**

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